

Strongly semi- $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano continuity, strongly semi- $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano retracts and decision making

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Abstract: In this paper, the notion of nano topological spaces is extended to $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano topological space. The concepts of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano open sets and weaker form of it in $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano topological space are introduced and investigated. The relations between these concepts are considered, and a definition for a $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano continuous function nano continuous function is provided. Several theorems and examples are presented to study generalizations of this concept. As an application get $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano retracts via $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano continuous functions. More examples and results are obtained. Finally, $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano topological space is used for correct decision-making.

Key words: $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano topological space; $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano continuous function, $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ -L-fuzzy nano retracts, decision making

1. Introduction

Rough set theory is a modern mathematical approach to incomplete knowledge. Rough set is formal approximation of a crisp set (i.e., conventional set) in terms of a pair of sets which give the lower and the upper approximation of the original set. The lower and upper approximation sets themselves are crisp sets in the standard version of rough set theory, but in other variations, the approximating sets may be fuzzy sets as well. Rough set theory is a new method that deals with vagueness and uncertainty emphasized in decision making. The theory of rough sets, proposed by Pawlak [4, 5], is an extension of the set theory for the study of intelligent systems characterized by insucient and in-complete information. Recent years have witnessed its wide applications in various elds such as: machine learning, knowledge discovery, data mining, expert systems, pattern recognition, granular computing, graph theory, algebraic systems, partially ordered sets [1, 3, 6]. In Pawlak’s rough set model [7], an equivalence relation is a key and primitive notion. This equivalence relation, however, seems to be a very stringent condition that may limit the application domain of the rough set model. In order to solve this problem, several authors have generalized the notion of approximation operators by using nonequivalence binary relations [10,14]. His has led to various other approximation operators [13, 15]. Fuzzy generalizations of rough sets were first introduced by Dubois and Prade [2]. Radzikowska and Kerre [8] considered L-fuzzy rough sets as a further generalization of the notion of rough sets. Thivagar [12] introduced the concept of nano topological spaces with respect to a subset X of a universe U , and the notion of a fuzzy retract was introduced by Rodabaugh [9]. Our aims of this paper, is to extend the notion of nano topological

spaces to $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano topological space and study some $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano open sets. The relationships between some weak and strong forms of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano open in $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano topological space are studied. In the second part we introduced $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano retracts as applications of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano topological space. Some interactions between these concepts are investigated. Finally we used $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano topological space to take the correct Decision making.

Definition 1.1.[5] Let U be a non-empty finite set of objects called the universal and R be an L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U . The pair (\mathcal{R}, U) is said to be the approximation space. Let $X \subseteq U$.

(1) The lower approximation of X with respect to calR is denoted by $L_{\mathcal{R}}(X)$, that is

$$L_{\mathcal{R}}(X) = \bigcap_{x \in U} \{(\mathcal{R}(x) : \mathcal{R}(x) \subseteq X\} \text{ where } \mathcal{R}(x) \text{ denote the equivalence class determined by } x.$$

(2) The upper approximation of X with respect to calR is denoted by $H_{\mathcal{R}}(X)$, that is

$$H_{\mathcal{R}}(X) = \bigcup_{x \in U} \{(\mathcal{R}(x) : \mathcal{R}(x) \cap X \neq \phi\},$$

(3) The boundary region of X with respect to calR is denoted by $B_{\mathcal{R}}(X)$, that is

$$B_{\mathcal{R}}(X) = H_{\mathcal{R}}(X) - L_{\mathcal{R}}(X). \text{ According to pawlak definitions, } X \text{ is called a rough set if } H_{\mathcal{R}}(X) \neq L_{\mathcal{R}}(X).$$

Definition 1.2.[11] Let U be an arbitrary universal set, L be a fuzzy lattice and \mathcal{R} be an L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U . Then for $X \subseteq U$, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X) = \{U, \phi, L_{\mathcal{R}}(X), H_{\mathcal{R}}(X), B_{\mathcal{R}}(X)\}$ is called the nano topology on U . We call $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X))$ is a nano topological spaces. the elements of $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X)$ are called a nano open sets and the complement of a nano open sets is called nano closed sets.

Definition 1.3.[12] Let $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X))$ and $(V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(Y))$ be two nano topological spaces. A mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(Y))$ is said to be nano continuous if $f^{-1}(B)$ is nano open set in U for every nano open set B in V .

2. $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano bitopological space and strongly semi- $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano continuity

Definition 2.1 Let U be an arbitrary universal set, L be a fuzzy lattice. A map $\text{calR} : U \times U \rightarrow L$ is called L -fuzzy relation on U . $R(x, y)$ is referred to as the degree of relation between x and y , where $(x, y) \in U \times U$. A fuzzy relation R is called:

- (1) Reflexive if $R(x, x) = 1_L, \forall x \in U$,
- (2) Symmetric if $R(x, y) = R(y, x), \forall x, y \in U$,
- (3) Transitive if $R(x, z) \geq \bigvee_{y \in U} ((R(x, y) \wedge R(y, z)))$, R is called L -fuzzy equivalence relation if it is reflexive, symmetric and transitive.

Example 2.1. Let $U = \{x, y, z\}$, $L = \{0_L, 0_L \leq \alpha \leq 1_L, 1_L\}$ and. If $R : U \times U \rightarrow L$ defined as follows:

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 1_L & \alpha \\ 1_L & 1_L & \alpha \\ \alpha & \alpha & 1_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Then R is L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U .

Definition 2.2. Let U be an arbitrary universal set, L be a fuzzy lattice and R be an L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U . With each L -fuzzy set λ on U , we associate two L -fuzzy sets, the lower and upper approximations of L -fuzzy set λ , respectively $L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda, H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda : U \rightarrow L$:

$$(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) = \bigwedge_{t \in U} ((\mathcal{R}(x, t))' \vee \lambda(t)) \text{ and } (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) = \bigvee_{t \in U} ((\mathcal{R}(x, t)) \wedge \lambda(t)), \forall x \in U.$$

The pair $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda, H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)$ is referred to as a generalized rough set of λ related to L , $(\mathcal{R}(x, t))'$ means the complement of the relation $\mathcal{R}(x, t)$.

Example 2.2. In Example 2.1 and if $\lambda \in L^U$ such that $\lambda(x) = 0.2, \lambda(y) = 0.4, \lambda(z) = 0.7$.

Then $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) = 0.2, (L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(y) = 0.2, (L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(z) = 0.5$ and $(H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) = 0.5, (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(y) = 0.5, (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(z) = 0.7$.

Definition 2.3. Let U be an arbitrary universal set, L be a fuzzy lattice and \mathcal{R} be an L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U . With each L -fuzzy set λ on U , the boundary approximations of L -fuzzy set λ , $B_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda : U \rightarrow L$ define by $(B_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) = (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) - (L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x), \forall x \in U$.

Example 2.3. In Example 2.2 $(B_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda) = (0.3, 0.3, 0.2)$.

Definition 2.4. Let U be an arbitrary universal set, L be a fuzzy lattice and \mathcal{R} be an L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U . With each L -fuzzy set λ on U , $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}_L, L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda, H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda, B_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda\}$ is called L -fuzzy nano topology on U . We call $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda))$ is called L -fuzzy nano topological space. The elements of $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)$ are called a nano open sets and the complement of a nano open sets is called nano closed sets.

Definition 2.5. Let U be an arbitrary universal set, L be a fuzzy lattice and \mathcal{R} be an L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U . With each L -fuzzy set λ on U , $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}_L, L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda, H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda, B_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda\}$ is called L -fuzzy nano topology on U . We call $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda))$ is called L -fuzzy nano topological space. The elements of $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)$ are called L -fuzzy nano open sets and $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda))'$ is the complement of an L -fuzzy nano open sets in $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X)$ is called L -fuzzy nano closed sets. The set $\beta = \{\underline{1}_L, L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda, B_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda\}$ is called a base for the L -fuzzy nano topology $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)$ on U respect to L -fuzzy set λ .

Example 2.4. In Example 2.2

$$\beta = \{1_L, (0.2, 0.2, 0.5), (0.3, 0.3, 0.2)\}. \text{ Then } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}_L, (0.2, 0.2, 0.5), (0.5, 0.5, 0.7), (0.3, 0.3, 0.2)\}.$$

Definition 2.6. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^*$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U . A system $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*(\lambda))$ consisting of an arbitrary universal set U with two L -fuzzy nano topologies $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)$ and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*(\lambda)$ on U is called an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space.

Example 2.5. Let $U = \{x, y, z\}, L = [0, 1], \lambda \in L^U$ such that $\lambda(x) = 0.2, \lambda(y) = 0.4, \lambda(z) = 0.7$. and. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^* : U \times U \rightarrow L$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U defined as follows:

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 1_L & 0.5 \\ 1_L & 1_L & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0.5 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}, R^* = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 0.6 & 0.5 \\ 0.6 & 1_L & 0.3 \\ 0.5 & 0.3 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}_L, (0.2, 0.2, 0.5), (0.5, 0.5, 0.7), (0.3, 0.3, 0.2)\}$, and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}_L, (0.2, 0.4, 0.5), (0.5, 0.4, 0.7), (0.3, 0.0, 0.2)\}$. Then $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\lambda))$ is an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space.

Definition 2.7. Let $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X))$ be L -fuzzy nano topological space with respect to X , where $\lambda, \mu, \zeta \in L^U$. Then,

(1) L -fuzzy nano interior of λ is defined by, $\mathcal{N}Int(\mu) = \bigvee \{\zeta \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) : \zeta \leq \mu\}$, (If a family of L -fuzzy nano topological space is contained in one productivity class, then the L -fuzzy nano interior operator is finitely productive on that family).

(2) L -fuzzy nano closure of λ is defined by, $\mathcal{N}Cl(\mu) = \bigwedge \{\eta \in (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda))' : \mu \leq \eta\}$. (A family of L -fuzzy nano topological space is said to be contained in one productivity class if the L -fuzzy nano closure operator is finitely productive on that family).

Example 2.6. In Example 2.4 let $\mu \in L^U$ such that $\mu(x) = 0.1, \mu(x) = 0.3, \mu(x) = 0.6.$, Then,

$$\mathcal{N}Int(\mu) = \bigvee \{\zeta \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) : \zeta \leq \mu\} = \underline{0}_L, \text{ and } \mathcal{N}Cl(\mu) = \bigwedge \{\eta \in (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda))' : \mu \leq \eta\} = (0.7, 0.7, 0.8).$$

If $\lambda, \mu \in L^U$, $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^*$ is L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U . A system $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu))$ consisting of a set U with two L -fuzzy nano topological spaces $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu)$ on U is called L -fuzzy nano bitopological space, if P is any L -fuzzy nano topological property, then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)-P$ (resp, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu)-P$) denote the property P with respect to L -fuzzy nano topology $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)$ (resp, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu)$).

As two the concepts and nomenclature, we shall write $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}-\mathcal{N}Int(\mu)$ and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}-\mathcal{N}Cl(\mu)$ to mean respectively the interior and closure of L -fuzzy nano μ with respect to the L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu))$

Definition 2.8. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^*$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U and Let μ L -fuzzy nano subset of L -fuzzy nano bitopological space with respect to X $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(X))$. Then, μ is called:

(1) A $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano semi open (briefly, $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})-\mathcal{N}FSO)$ of U if, $\mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}-\mathcal{N}Cl(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}-\mathcal{N}Int(\mu))$,

(2) A $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano pre open (briefly, $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})-\mathcal{N}FPPO)$ of U if, $\mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}-\mathcal{N}Int(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}-\mathcal{N}Cl(\mu))$,

(3) A $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano strongly semi open (briefly, $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})-\mathcal{N}FSSO)$ of U if, $\mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}-\mathcal{N}Int(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}-\mathcal{N}Cl(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}-\mathcal{N}Int(\mu)))$, or iff there exist $\nu \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}$ s.t. $\nu \leq \lambda \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}-\mathcal{N}Int(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}-\mathcal{N}Cl(\nu))$.

(4) A $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ - L -fuzzy nano pre semi open (briefly, $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})-\mathcal{N}FPSSO)$ of U if, $\mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}-\mathcal{N}Cl(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}-\mathcal{N}Int(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}-\mathcal{N}Cl(\mu)))$.

The complement of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})-\mathcal{N}FSO$ $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})-\mathcal{N}FPPO, ((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})-\mathcal{N}FSSO)$,

$((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSO})$ set is called a L -fuzzy nano semi closed (L -fuzzy nano pre closed, L -fuzzy nano strongly semi closed, L -fuzzy nano pre semi closed) set
 (briefly, $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSC}$, $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPC}$, $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSSC})$, $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSO})$) set in U .

Theorem 2.1 (1) Any union of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ set is a $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ set.
 (2) Any intersection of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSC}$ set is a $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSC}$ set.

Definition 2.9. Let $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(X))$ be L -fuzzy nano topological space with respect to X , where $\lambda, \mu, \zeta \in L^U$. Then,

- (1) L -fuzzy nano semi interior of λ is defined by, $\mathcal{NSint}(\mu) = \bigvee \{ \zeta \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) : \zeta \in \mathcal{NFSSO}, \zeta \leq \mu \}$
- (1) L -fuzzy nano semi closure of λ is defined by, $\mathcal{NScl}(\mu) = \bigwedge \{ \eta \in (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda))' : \eta \in \mathcal{NFSC}, \mu \leq \eta \}$
- (3) A $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - L$ -fuzzy nano less strongly semi open (briefly, $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFLSSO})$ of U if, there exists $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - L$ -fuzzy nano open ν s.t. $\nu \leq \mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NSint}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^* - \mathcal{NScl}(\nu))$.

Equivalently if, $\mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NSint}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^* - \mathcal{NScl}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\mu)))$, The complement of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFLSSO}$ set is called a L -fuzzy nano less strongly semi closed (briefly, $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFLSSC}$) set in U .

Theorem 2.2 (1) Any union of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFLSSO}$ (resp. $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPO}$) set is a $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFLSSO}$ (resp. $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPO}$) set.
 (2) Any intersection of $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFLSSC}$ (resp. $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPC}$) set is a $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFLSSC}$ (resp. $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPC}$) set.

Remark 2.1

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFO} & (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFC} & \\
 \downarrow & & \\
 (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSSO} & (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSSC} & \Rightarrow \quad ((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPO}) (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPC} \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 ((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSSO}) & (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFSC} & \Rightarrow \quad ((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSO}) (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSO}
 \end{array}$$

That none of the converse need be true as shown by the following example

Example 2.7. Let $U = \{x, y, z\}$, $L = [0, 1]$, $\lambda \in L^U$ such that $\lambda(x) = 0.1$, $\lambda(y) = 0.3$, $\lambda(z) = 0.5$. and. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^* : U \times U \rightarrow L$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{R} = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 0.7 & 0.8 \\ 0.7 & 1_L & 0.6 \\ 0.8 & 0.6 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{R}^* = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 0.9 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 1_L & 0.8 \\ 0.9 & 0.8 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) = \{ \underline{1_L}, \underline{0}, (0.1, 0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.2, 0.3) \}$, and

$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, (0.1, 0.1, 0.1), (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.4, 0.4)\}$. Then $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\lambda))$ is an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space., Then $A(x) = 0.4, A(y) = 0.4, A(z) = 0.4$ is $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ of U , but not $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFO}$, $B(x) = 0.1, B(y) = 0.1, B(z) = 0.1$ is $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFPO}$ and $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFPSO}$ of U , but neither $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ nor $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$, $C(x) = 0.3, C(y) = 0.4, C(z) = 0.1$ is $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFPSO}$ and $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ of U , but neither $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFPO}$ nor $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$.

Theorem 2.3 Let $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ is an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space. Then:

- (1) If λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO})$ set and $\lambda \leq \mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*} - \mathcal{NCl}(\lambda))$, then μ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO})$ set,
- (2) If λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSC})$ set and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*} - \mathcal{NCl}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\lambda)) \leq \mu \leq \lambda$, then μ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSC})$ set.

Proof (1) Let λ be an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO})$ set. Then, there exist $\nu \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}$ s.t. $\nu \leq \lambda \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*} - \mathcal{NCl}(\nu))$, since $\lambda \leq \mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*} - \mathcal{NCl}(\lambda))$, then $\nu \leq \lambda \leq \mu \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*} - \mathcal{NCl}(\lambda))$. So, μ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO})$ set.

(2) The same fashion

Definition 2.10. Let $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})$ be L -fuzzy nano topological space, where $V \subseteq U$ Then, $(V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V)$ is a subspace of L -fuzzy nano topological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})$ is defined by, $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V = \{\chi_V \wedge \zeta : \zeta \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}\}$.

such that $\chi_V : X \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is a characterisitc function define by $(\chi_V(x) = 1$ if $x \in V$ and $\chi_V(x) = 0$ if $x \notin V)$.

Theorem 2.4 Let $(V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})_V)$ is an subspace of L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})$ where $V \subseteq U$ and $\lambda \in L^V$ Then,

- (1) If λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO})$ set in U , then λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})_V) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ in V .
 - (2) If λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})_V) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ in V and χ_V is $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}) - \mathcal{NFO}$ in U ,
- then λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO})$ set in U .

Proof (1) Let λ be an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO})$ set in U . Then, there exist $\nu \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}$ s.t. $\nu \leq \lambda \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*} - \mathcal{NCl}(\nu))$, then we have $\chi_V \wedge \nu \leq \chi_V \wedge \lambda \leq \chi_V \wedge (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*} - \mathcal{NCl}(\nu)))$, then $\chi_V \wedge \nu \leq \lambda \leq ((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V - \mathcal{NInt}((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})_V - \mathcal{NCl}(\chi_V \wedge \nu)))$. Hence λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})_V) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ in V .

(2) Let λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})_V) - \mathcal{NFSSO}$ in V . Then, there exist $\chi_V \wedge \nu$ s.t. $\chi_V \wedge \nu \leq \lambda \leq (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V - \mathcal{NInt}((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})_V - \mathcal{NCl}(\chi_V \wedge \nu))$, since $\chi_V \wedge \nu$ is $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V - \mathcal{NFO}$ set, there exist $\nu \in (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}) - \mathcal{NFO}$ such that, $\chi_V \wedge \nu \leq \lambda \leq (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}})_V - \mathcal{NInt}((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*})_V - \mathcal{NCl}(\chi_V \wedge \nu)) \leq (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}} - \mathcal{NInt}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*} - \mathcal{NCl}(\chi_V \wedge \nu)))$ since $\chi_V \wedge \nu$ is $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}) - \mathcal{NFO}$ hence λ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}) - \mathcal{NFSSO})$ set in U .

Remark 2.2. The concepts of \mathcal{NFSSO} set and \mathcal{NFLSSO} set in L -fuzzy nano topological spaces are equivalent.

Example 2.8. Let $U = \{x, y, z\}$, $L = [0, 1]$, $\lambda, \mu \in L^U$ such that $\lambda(x) = 0.2$, $\lambda(y) = 0.4$, $\lambda(z) = 0.7$, $\mu(x) = 0.3$, $\mu(y) = 0.3$, $\mu(z) = 0.2$. and. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^* : U \times U \rightarrow L$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U defined as follows:

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 1_L & 0.5 \\ 1_L & 1_L & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0.5 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}, R^* = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 1_L & 0.6 \\ 1_L & 1_L & 0.6 \\ 0.6 & 0.6 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}, (0.2, 0.2, 0.5), (0.5, 0.5, 0.7), (0.3, 0.3, 0.2)\}$, and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}, (0.2, 0.4, 0.5), (0.5, 0.4, 0.7), (0.3, 0.0, 0.2)\}$. Then $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\lambda))$ is an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space. Then μ is \mathcal{NFSSO} set and \mathcal{NFLSSO} .

Definition 2.11. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^*$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U and let $\mathcal{R}_2, \mathcal{R}_2^*$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on V , $\lambda, \mu \in L^U$. A mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-continuous (resp. L -fuzzy nano-open), briefly, \mathcal{NFC} (resp. \mathcal{NP} open) mapping if $\forall \sigma \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu)$, $f^{\leftarrow}(\sigma) \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)$.

Definition 2.12. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^*$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U and let $\mathcal{R}_2, \mathcal{R}_2^*$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on V , $\lambda, \mu \in L^U$. A mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-pairwise continuous (resp. L -fuzzy nano-pairwise open), briefly, \mathcal{NFPC} (resp. \mathcal{NFP} open) mapping if $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu))$, $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu))$ ($f(\sigma) \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu)$, $\forall \sigma \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)$ and $f(\xi) \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu)$, $\forall \xi \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)$) are \mathcal{NF} -continuous (resp. \mathcal{NF} -open).

Example 2.9. Let $U = \{x, y, z\}$, $L = [0, 1]$, $\lambda \in L^U$ such that $\lambda(x) = 0.1$, $\lambda(y) = 0.3$, $\lambda(z) = 0.5$. and. Let $\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_1^* : U \times U \rightarrow L$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U defined as follows:

$$R_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 0.7 & 0.8 \\ 0.7 & 1_L & 0.6 \\ 0.8 & 0.6 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}, R_1^* = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 0.9 & 0.9 \\ 0.9 & 1_L & 0.8 \\ 0.9 & 0.8 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}, (0.1, 0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.2, 0.3)\}$, and

$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}, (0.1, 0.1, 0.1), (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.4, 0.4)\}$. Then $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda))$ is an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space. Also, Let $V = \{a, b, c\}$, $L = [0, 1]$, $\lambda \in L^U$ such that $\mu(x) = 0.3$, $\mu(y) = 0.2$, $\mu(z) = 0.4$. and. Let $\mathcal{R}_2, \mathcal{R}_2^* : U \times U \rightarrow L$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U defined as follows:

$$R_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 0.7 & 0.8 \\ 0.7 & 1_L & 0.9 \\ 0.8 & 0.9 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}, R_2^* = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 0.8 & 1_L \\ 0.8 & 1_L & 0.6 \\ 1_L & 0.6 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}, (0.3, 0.2, 0.2), (0.4, 0.4, 0.4), (0.1, 0.2, 0.2)\}$, and

$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}, (0.2, 0.2, 0.2), (0.4, 0.4, 0.4)\}$. Then $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\lambda))$ is an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space on V , and a mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu))$ define by $f(x) = b$, $f(y) = a$, $f(z) = c$, since $f^{\leftarrow}((0.3, 0.2, 0.2)) = (0.2, 0.3, 0.2) \notin \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)$. Then f is not L -fuzzy nano-pairwise continuous, and since $f((0.1, 0.3, 0.2)) = (0.3, 0.1, 0.2) \notin \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\lambda)$. Then f is not L -fuzzy nano-pairwise open.

Theorem 2.5 The product $f_1 \times f_2 : U_1 \times U_2 \rightarrow V_1 \times V_2$ of L -fuzzy nano-pairwise continuous mappings $f_1 : U_1 \rightarrow V_1$, $f_2 : U_2 \rightarrow V_2$ is L -fuzzy nano-pairwise continuous mapping.

Lemma 2.1 Let $g : X \rightarrow X \times Y$ be the graph of a mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$. Then, if λ be an L -fuzzy nano-open set of X and μ be an L -fuzzy nano-open set of Y , then $g^{\leftarrow}(\lambda \times \mu) = \lambda \wedge f^{\leftarrow}(\mu)$.

Theorem 2.6 Let $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-pairwise continuous and L -fuzzy nano-pairwise open mapping from an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda))$ into an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu))$, $\lambda \in L^U, \mu \in L^V$. Then,

- (1) If α is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) - NFSSO)$ set in U , then $f(\alpha)$ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu)) - NFSSO)$ set in V , and
- (2) If θ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu)) - NFSSO)$ set in V , then $f^{\leftarrow}(\theta)$ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) - NFSSO)$ set in U .

Proof (1) Let α be an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) - NFSSO)$ set in U . Then, there exist $\nu \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)$ s.t. $\nu \leq \lambda \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) - \mathcal{N}Int(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda) - \mathcal{N}Cl(\nu))$,

then we have $f(\nu) \leq f(\lambda) \leq f[\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) - \mathcal{N}Int(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda) - \mathcal{N}Cl(\nu))] \leq (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu) - \mathcal{N}Int(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu) - \mathcal{N}Cl(f(\nu)))$, since f is L -fuzzy nano-pairwise open mapping, then $f(\nu)$ is a $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu) - \mathcal{N}FO$ set and hence $f(\lambda)$ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu)) - NFSSO)$ set in V .

(2) By the same manner

Theorem 2.7 Let $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-pairwise continuous and L -fuzzy nano-pairwise open mapping from an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda))$ into an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu))$, $\lambda \in L^U, \mu \in L^V$. Then,

- (1) If α is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) - NFSSO)$ set in U , then $f(\alpha)$ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu)) - NFSSO)$ set in V , and
- (2) If θ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}(\mu)) - NFSSO)$ set in V , then $f^{\leftarrow}(\theta)$ is an $((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\lambda)) - NFSSO)$ set in U .

Proof Easy

Definition 2.13. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^*$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U and let $\mathcal{R}_2, \mathcal{R}_2^*$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on V . $\lambda, \mu \in L^U$.

(1) A mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-pairwise semi continuous (briefly \mathcal{NFPSC}) mapping if

$$\forall \theta \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu)) - \mathcal{NFS} \right) \text{ open set on } V, f^{\leftarrow}(\theta) \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFS} \right) \text{ open et on } U,$$

(2) A mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-pairwise pre continuous (briefly \mathcal{NFPSC}) mapping if

$$\forall \theta \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu)) - \mathcal{NFP} \right) \text{ open set on } V, f^{\leftarrow}(\theta) \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFP} \right) \text{ .open et on } U,$$

(3) A mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-pairwise strongly semi continuous (briefly \mathcal{NFPSSC}) mapping if

$$\forall \theta \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu)) - \mathcal{NFPSS} \right) \text{ open set on } V, f^{\leftarrow}(\theta) \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFPSS} \right) \text{ open et on } U,$$

(4) A mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-pairwise semi pre continuous (briefly \mathcal{NFPSPC}) mapping if

$$\forall \theta \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu)) - \mathcal{NFPSP} \right) \text{ open set on } V, f^{\leftarrow}(\theta) \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFPSP} \right) \text{ open et on } U.$$

Remark 2.2 For the mapping $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$ the following are valied:

$$\begin{aligned} f \text{ is } (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSC} &\Rightarrow f \text{ is } (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSC} \\ &\Downarrow \\ f \text{ is } (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSC} &\Rightarrow f \text{ is } (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSSC} \\ &\Downarrow \\ &\Rightarrow f \text{ is } (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*) - \mathcal{NFPSPC} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.14. Let α be an L -fuzzy nano-set of L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda))$, $\lambda \in L^U$. We define the following sets:

$$(1) \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)^\circ = \bigvee \left\{ \nu : \nu \leq \alpha, \nu \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFPSS} \right) \text{ open set on } U \right\},$$

$$(2) \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)^- = \bigwedge \left\{ \nu : \nu \geq \alpha, \nu \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFPSS} \right) \text{ closed set on } U \right\},$$

we call $\left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)^\circ$ the $\left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFPSS} \right)$ interior set of α and

$\left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)^-$ the $\left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFPSS} \right)$ closure set of α .

Theorem 2.8 Let α be an L -fuzzy nano-set of L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda))$, $\lambda \in L^U$. Then,

$$(1) \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)^- = \alpha \text{ iff } \alpha \in \left((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) - \mathcal{NFPSS} \right) \text{ closed set on } U,$$

(2) $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ = \alpha$ iff $\alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{NFSS}\right)$ open set on U .

Proof It is direct from Theorem 2.2.

Proposition 2.1 Let α and θ be an L -fuzzy nano-sets of L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $\left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right)$, $\lambda \in L^U$. Then lowing statements are true:

(1) $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha))^\circ \leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ \leq \alpha \leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^- \leq (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha))^-$,

(2) If $\alpha \leq \theta$, then $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ \leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\theta)\right)^\circ$,

and $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^- \leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\theta)\right)^-$,

(3) $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^-\right)^- = \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^-$,

and $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ\right)^\circ = \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ$.

(4) $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha \vee \theta)\right)^- \geq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^- \vee \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\theta)\right)^-$,

and $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha \vee \theta)\right)^\circ \geq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ \wedge \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\theta)\right)^\circ$.

Proof It is direct from Definition 2.13 and Theorem 2.8.

Theorem 2.9 Let α be an L -fuzzy nano-set of L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $\left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right)$, $\lambda \in L^U$. Then,

(1) $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ = \alpha$ iff $\alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{NFSS}\right)$ open set on U ,

(2) $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^- = \alpha$ iff $\alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{NFSS}\right)$ closed set on U .

Proof It is direct from Theorem 2.2.

Theorem 2.10 Let α be an L -fuzzy nano-set of L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $\left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right)$, $\lambda \in L^U$. Then,

(1) $\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ\right)' = \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)'\right)^-$,

(2) $\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^-\right)' = \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)'\right)^\circ$.

Proof (1) by Proposition 2.1, we have

$\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ \leq \alpha$, then $\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ\right)' \geq \alpha'$.

Since $\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha)\right)^\circ\right)' \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)\right) - \mathcal{NFSS}\right)$ closed set on U , then

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^- &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^- \right)' \\ &= \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)' \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, By Proposition 2.1, we have

$$\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^- \geq \alpha', \text{ then } \left(\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^- \right)' \leq \alpha,$$

Since $\left(\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^- \right)' \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NFSS} \right)$ open set on U , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^- \right)' &= \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^- \right)' \right)' \\ &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \end{aligned}$$

Then, $\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)' \leq \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^-$, hence,

$$\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)' = \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(\alpha) \right)' \right)^-$$

(2) in (1) if replace α by α' we get a result.

Lemma 2.2. Let α be an L -fuzzy nano-set of L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda))$, $\lambda \in L^U$. Then,

- (1) $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}Int(\alpha) \right)' = \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}Cl(\alpha') \right),$
- (2) $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}Cl(\alpha) \right)' = \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}Int(\alpha') \right).$

Theorem 2.11 Let $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda))$, $(V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$ and $(W, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_3}(\sigma), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_3^*}^*(\sigma))$ be L -fuzzy nano bitopological spaces.

$f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$ is \mathcal{NFPSC} and

$g : (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu)) \rightarrow (W, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_3}(\sigma), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_3^*}^*(\sigma))$ is \mathcal{NFPSC} mapping,

$gf : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) \rightarrow (W, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_3}(\sigma), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_3^*}^*(\sigma))$ is \mathcal{NFPSC} mapping.

Theorem 2.12 Let $f : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda)) \rightarrow (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$ is said to L -fuzzy nano-pairwise mapping from an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda))$ into L -fuzzy nano bitopological space $(V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu))$, $\lambda \in L^U$, $\mu \in L^V$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

(1) f is $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*)$ - \mathcal{NFPSSC} ,
 (2) $\forall \alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ closed set on V , $f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha) \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NFSS} \right)$ closed set on U ,

(3) $\forall \theta \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ open set on U ,

$$f \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(\theta) \right)^- \right) \leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta)) \right),$$

(4) $\forall \alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ open set on V ,

$$\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)) \right)^- \leq f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(\alpha) \right),$$

(5) $\forall \alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ open set on V ,

$$f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NInt}(\alpha) \right) \leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)) \right)^{\circ}.$$

Proof (1) \Leftrightarrow (2) It is clear

(2) \Leftrightarrow (3) $\forall \theta \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ open set on U . Then $\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta))$ is $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ closed set on V , by (2) we have

$f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta)) \right)$ is $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NFSS} \right)$ closed set on U , since $\theta \leq f^{\leftarrow}(f(\theta)) \leq f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta)) \right)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(\theta) \right)^- &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(f^{\leftarrow}(f(\theta))) \right)^- \\ &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \left(f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta)) \right) \right) \right)^- \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 2.8 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(\theta) \right)^- &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \left(f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta)) \right) \right) \right)^- \\ &= f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} f \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(\theta) \right)^- \right) &\leq f \left(f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta)) \right) \right) \\ &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(\theta)) \right). \end{aligned}$$

(3) \Leftrightarrow (4) $\forall \alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ open set on V , by (3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} f \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(\alpha) \right)^- \right) &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha))) \right) \\ &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(\alpha) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(\alpha) \right)^- \leq f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(\alpha) \right)$$

(4) \Leftrightarrow (5) $\forall \alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ closed set on V , then by (4) we have

$$\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)) \right)^- \leq f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)) \right)$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \left(f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(\mathcal{Cl}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha))) \right) \right)' &\leq \left(\left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)) \right)^- \right) \right)' \\ &= \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)) \right)^- \right)', \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 2.10 (2), we have,

$$\begin{aligned} f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(\mathcal{Cl}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha))) \right) \right)' &\leq \left(\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)) \right)^- \right)' \\ &= \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NF}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)) \right)^\circ \end{aligned}$$

From Lemma 2.2 (2) we have $\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NInt}(\alpha) = \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(\alpha') \right)'$.

This implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \left(f^{\leftarrow} \left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NInt}(\alpha) \right) &= f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(\alpha') \right)' \\ &= \left(f^{\leftarrow} \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NCl}(\alpha') \right) \right)', \\ &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha))^\circ \right). \end{aligned}$$

(5) \Leftrightarrow (1) $\forall \alpha \in \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NF} \right)$ open et on V , then $\alpha = \left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NInt}(\alpha)$,

Subsequently by (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha) &= \left(f^{\leftarrow} \left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right) - \mathcal{NInt}(\alpha) \right) \\ &\leq \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha))^\circ \right). \\ &\leq f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha). \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha) = \left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{N}(f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha))^{\circ} \right)$$

By Theorem 2.8 we have $f^{\leftarrow}(\alpha)$ is $\left(\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) - \mathcal{NFSS} \right)$ open set on U , thus f is $\left(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^* \right)$ - \mathcal{NFSSC} .

3. Strongly semi- $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*)$ -L-fuzzy nano retracts

Definition 3.1. Let $\left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right)$ be an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space, $\lambda \in L^U$ and $Y \subseteq U$. We define the family $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y = \{ \alpha \wedge \chi_Y : \alpha \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \}$ is an L -fuzzy nano topology on Y , we refer to $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y)$ as an L -fuzzy nano topological subspace. ($\chi_Y(x) = 1$ if $x \in Y$ and $\chi_Y(x) = 0$ if $x \notin Y$).

Example 3.1. In Example 2.7 If $Y = \{x, y\} \subseteq U$. Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y = \{ \underline{1}_L, \underline{0}, (0.2, 0.2), (0.5, 0.5), (0.3, 0.3) \}$ is an L -fuzzy nano topological subspace on Y , and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y = \{ \underline{1}_L, \underline{0}_L, (0.2, 0.4), (0.5, 0.4), (0.3, 0.0) \}$ is an L -fuzzy nano topological subspace on Y . Also, $(Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y)$ is an L -fuzzy nano bitopological subspace on Y .

Definition 3.2. Let $\left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right)$ be an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space, $\lambda \in L^U$ and $Y \subseteq U$. Then L -fuzzy nano bitopological subspace $(Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y)$ is called a L -fuzzy nano pairwise retract of $\left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right)$ if there exists L -fuzzy nano pairwise continuous mapping $r : \left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y)$ s.t. $r(a) = a \forall a \in Y$. In this case r is called an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retraction.

Example 3.2 Let $U = \{x, y, z\}$, $Y = \{x, y\}$, $\lambda, \mu \in L^U$ such that $\lambda(x) = 0.2, \lambda(y) = 0.4, \lambda(z) = 0.7, \mu(x) = 0.3, \mu(y) = 0.3, \mu(z) = 0.2$. and. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}^* : U \times U \rightarrow L$ be two L -fuzzy equivalence relation on U defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{R} = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 1_L & 0.5 \\ 1_L & 1_L & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0.5 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{R}^* = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 0.6 & 0.6 \\ 0.6 & 1_L & 0.6 \\ 0.6 & 0.6 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Then $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) = \{ \underline{1}_L, \underline{0}_L, (0.2, 0.2, 0.5), (0.5, 0.5, 0.7), (0.3, 0.3, 0.2) \}$, and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*(\lambda) = \{ \underline{1}_L, \underline{0}_L, (0.2, 0.4, 0.5), (0.5, 0.4, 0.7), (0.3, 0.0, 0.2) \}$. Then $(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}^*(\lambda))$ is an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space. Then $r : \left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y)$ s.t. $r(a) = a \forall a \in Y$ is called an not L -fuzzy nano pairwise retraction. (because $r^{\leftarrow}((0.2, 0.2)) = (0.2, 0.2, 0.2) \notin \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)$ so $r : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_Y)$ is not L -fuzzy nano continuous mapping).

Theorem 3.1 Let $\left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}^*(\lambda) \right)$ be an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space on U , $\lambda \in L^U$ and Let $\left(V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_2^*}^*(\mu) \right)$, $\mu \in L^V$ be an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space on V . If $A \subseteq U$ is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retract of U and $B \subseteq V$ is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retract V , then $A \times B$ is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retract of $U \times V$.

Proof Because $A \subseteq U$ is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retract of U then, there exists L -fuzzy nano continuous mapping $r_1 : \left(U, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu)) \right) \rightarrow \left(A, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_A, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_A) \right)$ s.t $r_1(a) = a \forall a \in A$, then $r_1 : (U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (A, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_A))$ and $r_1 : \left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu) \right) \rightarrow \left(A, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_A) \right)$ are L -fuzzy nano continuous mappings. Also $B \subseteq U$ is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retract of V then, there exists L -fuzzy nano continuous mapping $r_2 : \left(V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu)) \right) \rightarrow \left(B, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_B, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_B) \right)$ s.t $r_2(b) = b \forall b \in B$, then $r_2 : (V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda)) \rightarrow (B, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_B))$ and $r_2 : \left(V, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu) \right) \rightarrow \left(B, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_B) \right)$ are L -fuzzy nano continuous mappings, by Theorem 2.5, we have $r_1 \times r_2 : (U \times V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda))) \rightarrow (A \times B, ((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_A), (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_B)))$, $r_1 \times r_2 : \left(U \times V, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu)) \right) \rightarrow \left(A \times B, ((\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_A), (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_B)) \right)$ and are L -fuzzy nano pairwise continuous mapping, and $(r_1 \times r_2)(a, b) = (a, b) \forall (a, b) \in A \times B$, hence $A \times B$ is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retract of $U \times V$.

Theorem 3.2 Let $\left(U, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu) \right)$ be an L -fuzzy nano bitopological space on U , $\lambda \in L^U$, $A \subseteq U$ and $r : \left(U, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu)) \right) \rightarrow \left(A, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_A, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_A) \right)$ be a mapping s.t $r(a) = a \forall a \in A$. The the graph $g : \left(U, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu)) \right) \rightarrow (U \times A, \theta_1, \theta_2)$ of r which defined by $g(x) = (x, r(x))$ L -fuzzy nano pairwise continuous mapping iff r is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retract, where θ_j is an L -fuzzy nano product bitopology generated by $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu))$ and $(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_A, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_A)$ ($j = 1, 2$).

Proof Since $g : \left(U, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu)) \right) \rightarrow (U \times A, \theta_1, \theta_2)$ is L -fuzzy nano pairwise continuous mapping and will prove that $r : \left(U, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu)) \right) \rightarrow \left(A, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) \wedge \chi_A, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}^*}(\mu) \wedge \chi_A) \right)$ is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retraction. So let ρ be an L -fuzzy nano open set of A . By Lemma 2.1 we have $r^{\leftarrow}(\rho) = 1_L \wedge r^{\leftarrow}(\rho) = g^{\leftarrow}(1_L \times \rho)$. Since g is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise continuous and $1_L \times \rho$ is θ_j is an L -fuzzy nano open set in $U \times A$, Then $r^{\leftarrow}(\rho) = g^{\leftarrow}(1_L \times \rho)$ is an L -fuzzy nano open set of U , hence r is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise continuous and therefore r is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retraction.

Conversely Since r is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise retraction. and will prove that g is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise continuous. So let $\rho \times v$ be an L -fuzzy nano open set of $U \times A$. By Lemma 2.1 we have $g^{\leftarrow}(\rho \times v) = \rho \wedge r^{\leftarrow}(v)$. Since ρ is an L -fuzzy nano open set in U and $r^{\leftarrow}(v)$ is an L -fuzzy nano open set in U , then $\rho \wedge r^{\leftarrow}(v)$ is an L -fuzzy nano open set in U , hence $g : \left(U, (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1}(\lambda), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}_1^*}(\mu)) \right) \rightarrow (U \times A, \theta_1, \theta_2)$ is an L -fuzzy nano pairwise continuous.

4. An application of an L -fuzzy nano topology in decision making

We suggest a new technique for medical diagnosis by L -fuzzy nano topology. The principle of maximum membership and minimum nonmembership to make right decision have more important roles here.

Step 1 State the set of criteria $U = \{\text{Viral Fever, Malaria, Typhoid}\}$ and let x, y, z are three patient

Step 2 The set of decision $\lambda \in L^U$, define by $\lambda = \{(0.7, 1], (0.4, 0.7], (0.1, 0.4]\}$. such that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)(x) \in (0.7, 1]$. that mean the patient (x) Severe injury by Viral Fever, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)(x) \notin (0.7, 1]$ that mean The injury is not serious by Viral Fever and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)(y) \in (0.4, 0.7]$. that mean the patient (y) Severe injury by Malaria, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)(y) \notin (0.4, 0.7]$ that mean the injury is not serious by Malaria and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)(z) \in (0.1, 0.4]$. that mean the patient (z) Severe injury by Typhoid, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda)(z) \notin (0.1, 0.4]$ that mean the injury is not serious by Typhoid

Step 3 criterion decision making fuzzy equivalence relation R on U defined as follows:

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 1_L & 1_L & 0.5 \\ 1_L & 1_L & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0.5 & 1_L \end{pmatrix}$$

Such that $R(x, y) (R(x, z), R(y, z))$ that mean that the degree of the patient injury by Viral Fever and Malaria (that mean that the degree of the patient injury by Viral Fever and Typhoid, That mean that the degree of the patient injury by Malaria, Typhoid).

Step 4 define upper and lower for the set of decision

$$(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) = \bigwedge_{t \in U} ((\mathcal{R}(x, t))' \vee \max(\lambda(t))) \text{ and } (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) = \bigvee_{t \in U} ((\mathcal{R}(x, t)) \wedge \max(\lambda(t))), \forall x \in U.$$

Then $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(\text{Viral Fever}) = 0.5$, $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(\text{Malaria}) = 0.5$, $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(\text{Typhoid}) = 0.4$ and $(H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(\text{Viral Fever}) = 1$, $(H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(\text{Malaria}) = 1$, $(H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(\text{Typhoid}) = 0.5$.

Step 5, L -fuzzy nano topology, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{R}}(\lambda) = \{\underline{1}_L, \underline{0}, (1, 1, 0.5), (0.5, 0.5, 0.4), (0.5, 0.5, 0.1)\}$

Step 6 Right decision making $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda) + (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)2(x), \forall x \in U$,

$$((L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) + (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x)2, (L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(y) + (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(y)2, (L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(z) + (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(z)2) = (0.75, 0.75, 0.45)$$

Step 7 the decision $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x) + (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(x)2 = 0.75 \in (0.7, 1]$, then that mean the patient (x) Severe injury by Viral Fever and $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(y) + (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(y)2 = 0.75$, that mean the patient (y) Severe injury by Malaria, $(L_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(z) + (H_{\mathcal{R}}\lambda)(z)2 = 0.45$ that mean the patient (z) Severe injury by Typhoid.

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